

Review Paper on Android App for Professional Networking and Resume Sharing

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Abstract: Most of the communication in today’s world is done through portable devices like mobiles, tablets, etc. Similarly the Internet gets most of the traffic from portable devices. Hence there is a need for Professional Communication and recruitment to go mobile. This paper intends to throw light on the previous work done in this field and to propose a light weight Professional Networking App that simplifies employee referral, standardizes and enhances professional communication.

Keywords: Android OS, Mobile Computing, Push Messaging, Resume Sharing, Chat Interface, Bluetooth.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social networking field has seen a steep increase due to new upcoming apps in the market day by day but compared to that professional networking is still unchallenged. There are many aspects in which professional networking needs to improve. This paper focuses on some of those improvements.

Recruitment process is an important exercise carried out in all the companies on all the levels. To make recruitment process fruitful, an efficient Human Resource Management (HRM) is required. This paper explains about an android application which helps to simplify HRM by providing an efficient chat interface and fast yet reliable resume sharing using various methods. This paper also throws light on some of the existing apps for the same, their advantages and disadvantages.

II. DESIGN

A. Chat

Push messaging provides an important aspect of server to device communication, and we specifically focus on the integration of cloud computing with mobile devices through the use of push-based technologies [2].

The main purpose of chat is nothing but communication between the users. Some of the basic features are:

- Instant Messaging
- Send Files

- Send Contacts
- Send Images

The basic idea behind how chat works can be understood from the following diagram using Apple Push Notification services (APNS):

Fig. 1 Simple Chat Structure [8]

A Chat Server is required to coordinate stuff between different devices [6]. Fig. 1 shows different components used in chat application.

JOIN. When a user signs up in the Login screen, his nickname, his secret code, and his device token is sent to the server. The server adds a record for this user to the list of active users. From then on, any messages sent by members of that same chat room will also be pushed to this new user [6].

LEAVE. This is the opposite of JOIN. The user can press the Exit button in the Chat screen to leave the chat. A LEAVE command is sent to the server which removes the user from the list of active users. From then on, no more notifications will be pushed to this user[6].

MESSAGE. When a user presses the Save button on the Compose screen, the new text message is sent to the server. The server will then convert these messages into push notifications, one for each member of that chat room, and passes them on to APNS. A few seconds later, APNS pushes these messages to those devices [6].

UPDATE. This lets the server know that a user has received a new device token. The token may change from time to time and if that happens, the server needs know [6].

The popularity of wireless communication application is increased specially in the ISM band which provides services for free. Bluetooth is one of the technology in unlicensed band which becomes very useful now a days in many short range application because of its advantages like low power consumption, low cost, low size, universal applicability, multiple simultaneous link [1].

The Android platform includes support for the Bluetooth network stack, which allows a device to wirelessly exchange data with other Bluetooth devices. Fig. 2 shows step-by-step process for Bluetooth file transfer. The application framework provides access to the Bluetooth functionality through the Android Bluetooth APIs. These APIs let applications wirelessly connect to other Bluetooth devices, enabling point-to-point and multipoint wireless features [7].

Using the Bluetooth APIs, an Android application can perform the following [7]:

- Scan for other Bluetooth devices
- Query the local Bluetooth adapter for paired Bluetooth devices
- Fig. 3 shows list of paired devices
- Establish RFCOMM channels
- Connect to other devices through service discovery
- Transfer data to and from other devices
- Manage multiple connections
- Fig. 4 shows a complete Bluetooth transfer.

Fig. 2 Flowchart of File Transfer Using Bluetooth [9]

Fig. 3 Bluetooth Paired Devices List [9]

Working

Fig. 4 Details of File Sent [9]

III. CHRONOLGY

This section of the paper deals with the chronological development of the recruitment process.

Wikipedia defines recruitment as “**Recruitment** refers to the overall process of attracting, selecting and appointing suitable candidates for jobs within an organization, either permanent or temporary. Recruitment can also refer to processes involved in choosing individuals for unpaid positions, such as voluntary roles or training programs” [3].

Social recruiting has a major advantage over traditional recruiting: it’s more human. Compared to the “post a job; wait for hundreds of resumes; let ATS filter through keywords; never get back to anyone” process many use today, social recruiting is a transparent, active approach where only the best candidates are sourced. In addition, recruiters can determine first impressions and cultural fit — even perform a bit of a background check — before approaching the candidate [4].

Hence, this paper explains the recruitment process as-

A. Traditional Approach

According to traditional approach, in correspondence to an advertisement, many people visit the recruitment area, submit hard-copies of resumes and wait hours long for interview and final selection list.

This is a very time consuming task, thus the efficiency is low.

B. Modern Approach

“Smart phones access to countless applications and virtually any web page. Job candidates the world over are glued to their phones. Interact in their space by optimizing your careers portal, providing ample information about your company online, and even leveraging older phone features like SMS for recruiting”[5].

In modern recruitment process, resumes are sent to the company, and only a specific amount of people are selected which are then eligible for further rounds of process.

Thus a wastage of time and effort is avoided using modern approach of recruitment process.

IV. SIMILAR APPLICATIONS

This paper is intended to take a brief study of some of the apps on android app stores and proposes an app that provides users with more useful features.

This paper here, explains some of the apps as,

A. Smart Recruitment

Smart Recruitment is a specialist recruitment company operating in the Driving, Industrial, Office, Technical & Catering sectors. We provide temporary and permanent recruitment solutions to a broad range of clients throughout the UK from our dedicated branches in Derby, Nottingham, Leicester, Walsall, Birmingham, Exeter & Bristol [10].

This app is all about recruitment facilities in **UK only**. It does not in any way simplify the recruitment process but helps the company to get more job proposals.

B. Super Resume Builder

Super Resume Builder, Resume Maker or bio-data maker is a utility that helps you create your resume instantly so that you can get the job you wish [11].

After filling in the information you can click on generate button to generate it in PDF format and then you can Email it or share it to any other pre- installed app (Dropbox, Google Drive etc.) on your device [11].

This app provides the facilities of resume builder and sharer. But sharing comes with constraints, i.e. it enables only sharing of resumes over in-built apps in user’s device for example e-mail, cloud storing etc.

V. PROBLEMS IN AVAILABLE APPS AND SUMMARIZED FEATURES OF PROPOSED APP

- The majority of apps in regards to recruitment and/or HRM on various app stores of Android basically focus on resume building and sharing via e-mail.
- The app stores lack an app that gives an efficient chat interface along with powerful resume generator and sharer with variety of sharing choices.
- The paper defines a detailed report of an app that can provide user with a user-friendly chat interface.
- It can also provide a large amount of templates along with a custom template for resume building.
- And nevertheless many sharing options like e-mail, Bluetooth and in-app sharing.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The paper in brief gives an explanation for a need of an application for professional networking with resume building and sharing. The paper also explains the whereabouts of the proposed application, thus chronologically explaining the development of the app and its future scope.

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